

Effect Of Retirement Counselling On Health, Economic And Sociological Adjustments Of Staff Of Tertiary Institution In Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the “Effect of Retirement Counselling on Health, Economic and Sociological Adjustments of Tertiary Institution Staff in Taraba State, Nigeria”. The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of retirement counselling on health, economic and sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of all tertiary institutions staff in Taraba State. 40 respondents were stratified and purposively selected for the study. The study used Quasi Experimental Design (QED) specifically the pretest-posttest design. Data was collected primarily using research instrument titled Retirement Counselling on Health, Economic and Sociological Adjustments Questionnaire tagged (RCHESAQ). Descriptive Statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while paired samples t-test was used to test the hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Findings revealed that retirement counselling has significant effect on health, economic and sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff. It was recommended that Counsellors should utilize retirement counselling practices alongside conventional methods to create a more inclusive and effective therapeutic environment on health, economic and sociological adjustments of tertiary institution staff among others.

Keywords: Retirement counselling, Health, Economic, Sociological and Tertiary Institution

INTRODUCTION

The statutory retirement age in Nigeria is 60 years or 35 years of unbroken active service, whichever comes first. After retirement, civil servants are entitled to benefits such as gratuity and pension. However, for decades, State governments in the country have had challenges paying retirees’ gratuities and pensions. These challenges have made retirement from civil service dreadful to intending retirees. Consequently, the federal government of Nigeria adopted the contributory pension scheme in 2004 to replace the defined benefit pension scheme that was operational. The scheme was amended for better efficiency in 2014. Nevertheless, most States in the country are yet to adopt the new scheme (Adetunde, Derby & Imhonopi 2018).

This is not different in Taraba state especially among tertiary institution staff particularly Taraba State University whose preparedness for retirement after active service has been on the front burner. Consequently, series of strike actions were embarked upon by both academic and non-academic staff of the institution to drive home the demand for a pension scheme that would guarantee job security to mitigate impending health, economic and sociological hardships faced by retirees after active service to the nation. Oftentimes, retirees suffer health problems ranging from high blood pressure, malnutrition,

eye problems as well as other general health problems associated with advancement in age and so on. On the other hand, they are faced with sociological problems such as isolation, low recreational activities, decline invitation to social gathering and likely low religious activities as a result of low or poor economic stability. These challenges have led many retirees to their early graves without enjoying the fruit of their labour, hence the need for caution and deliberate intention for adequate preretirement preparedness to adjust to life after active service especially among tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria. (Menchak, Ajai, Mshelia, Usman & Yawe, 2023).

The need to adjust to retirement life should be considered as a critical issue both by employers and employees. Today, the payment of pension is becoming increasingly challenging for all tiers of government to cope with. Hence, it is not strange to see the government owing pensioners several months of arrears. It has therefore become necessary for employees to plan for their retirement early because of unforeseen circumstances, such as sudden unexpected, ailments setting in as a result of old age, high inflation rate, exchange rate volatility, mass unemployment and high economic uncertainties (Amune, Aidenojie & Obinyan 2015). Retirement is viewed to differently by different people. While some persons view it positively and await it with happiness, others have negative perceptions about retirement as they associate that stage of life with boredom, economic suffering, ill health and death.

Consequently, such individuals experience a sense of loneliness and loss of status. Retirement is a necessary end which every worker must anticipate, whether in the public sector or in the private sector (Onoyas, 2013). Abdullahi, (2002) as cited by Amune et al (2015), opined that, workers themselves do not give early planning and management of postretirement conditions, the considerable priority it deserves. As a result of unpreparedness, many have faced lots of psychosomatic problems and some exhibit psycho-phobic reactions. Today, civil servants in both public and private sectors in Nigeria perceive retirement as the most intractable problem. Oneye (2012) also noted that retirement from work often create a lot of problems for retirees. These problems range from sudden loss of income, financial insufficiency and anxiety, deteriorating health conditions, anxiety about suitable post-retirement accommodation to problem of learning new survival skills for post-retirement life.

Machima (2012), opined that, retirement counselling is a trustworthy relationship between the retirees and the professional counsellor in which the counsellor who is the helper assist the retirees to overcome their problems. The focus of retirement counselling is to assist the retirees and all family members who are equally victims to gain insight into their feeling concerning retirement so that they can explore alternative ways that could help to enhance their emotional stability. Adejare, Dalhatu, Ayelabowo & Yusuf (2019), pointed out some areas in which retirees could be counselled by the counsellor to include: Accommodation Problems, Children School Fees, Psychological Adjustment to change in economic status, adjustment to loss of power and prestige. Other areas to counsel them on include; How to embark on independent business, how to make extra income after retirement, Community work, Volunteers work, Domestic problems, Marital adjustment, Physical and mental health, how to maintain adequate social contacts, Choice of hobbies and second round job amongst others. Retirement does not necessarily mean that the retiree is tired, one can be retired not tired for active service. They may still want to work for financial or emotional reasons. The counsellor should be able to plan relevant counselling programme and strategies that will be of importance and value to retiree for proper adjustment to economic and psychological problems as to be able to see life as meaningful (Baba 2010).

Isaacson as cited by Nagodi (2013), has given a number of strategies which counsellors should consider while counselling with the retired people. These include:

- Recognizing the fact that many factors have and will continue to encourage people to continue working well over age 65.
- Inadequate retirement and pension programs, continuing inflationary and economic trends, and the desire to supplement income will cause problems for retirees.
- Many retirees still posse skills and knowledge acquired from a lifetime of work that has great value to future generation of workers.
- The counsellor should search for new fields of endeavour or new opportunities in which the

individual can apply his/her competencies and skills acquired over many years of productive work.

- There is also the need to assist the retired workers to obtain a broader view of the world of work and make choices in consonance with their abilities, interest, and values depending of course on their physical and mental strengths.
- Counsellors can help retirees to develop social relationship skills which have remained largely unexplored during active working lives.
- A number of leisure activities which may be rewarding in health, social and psychologically can be explored for successful adjustment in retirement life.
- In addition to above Akinade (2011) has given tips which may give meaning to the life of a retiree and which counsellors could use to prepare the retirees mentally to be prepared for a life in retirement. Some of the tips are:
- A daily bread so guaranteed for the retiree and the retirees immediate family, that is taken for granted.
- A residence with a quality that is commensurate with the terminal one during active service, at least socially and psychologically.
- Guaranteed presence of other essentials of life so that their consumption would not need formal planning.
- A self and family health situation that is under control.
- One's social acceptance by self, by the immediate society of retirement life.
- The will to live to love and to be selfless service.
- And the absence of fear in any form be it fear of situational insufficiency, fear of topical adequacy, fear of loss or fear of psychic attack among others.

Adjustment can be defined as the ability to accommodate, finding the middle ground, cooperate and get along with oneself, surroundings and the others which is influenced by social, psychological and biological factors (Manesh, Alibazi, Ranjbaran, Por, Najafi & Khoshniyat 2017). Similarly, Singh, Edboh & Dhingra (2014), opined that, adjustment is a process by which an individual learns certain ways of behaviour to accommodate and cope the situation which he/she attains through harmony with his/her social environment. Adjustment for retirees could therefore mean finding the middle ground or the right balance as regarding their health, economic and social life in order to navigate through life challenges to live a low and simple life after retirement. This may go a long way to help retired secondary school teachers live a stress free life where ever they choose to settle down after active service life.

Problem Statement

The rate at which retired staff suffer various impediments ranging from psychological to social problems today appears to be on the increase. Despite efforts by governments, religious organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and spirited individuals to support retirees in Taraba State, challenges among retirees subsists in the country. Literature sources reveal that retirees from various walks of life suffer health, economic, emotional trauma, depression, negative self-concept and low self-esteem. Challenges of retirees' especially in the education sector are common in Taraba State. Many tertiary institution retirees' in Taraba State are not immune to the effect of health, economic and social adjustments. This could lead to situations where bread-winners would no longer be able to provide the basic needs of their families. It is observed that some of the problems encountered by retired staff of tertiary institution and other civil servants in the state include lack of prompt payment of gratuity and pensions as at when due, stress and coping skills among others. The researcher assumed these associated problems seem to have effects or impact greatly on the internal organization of the family. This study therefore seeks to determine the effect of retirement counselling on health, economic and sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

The purpose of the study was to:

1. determine the effect of retirement counselling on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

2. determine the effect of retirement counselling on economic adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.
3. determine the effect of retirement counselling on sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Behavioural Counselling Theory of Krumboltz and Thoresen

In a bid to find an appropriate counselling approach, Krumboltz and Thoresen (1969) deviated slightly from the cognitive or mental process principle and psychoanalytic approach to a more contractual form of dealing with behaviour problems. Behavioural theory sees man as a being that has the potential to change his behaviour to solve any problem presented to him by his environment. This theory believes that since behaviour is a function of heredity and environment, it can be changed through learning or relearning. Problems of maladaptive adjustment arise from inappropriate learning experiences or faulty pattern of imbibing knowledge. Characteristically, behavioural counselling maintains that man's behaviour is learned and is therefore subject to change through the same process. Secondly, specific changes in a man's environment can help in changing relevant behaviours which can only be tackled by altering the relevant changes in the environment.

Burgess's Activity Theory

The Burgess's Activity Theory, formulated by Tinsley and Tinstey (1987) is one of the most popular theories of retirement. According to this theory, individuals with a large number of roles are believed to be better equipped to cope with the loss of single role and interpersonal activity which is regarded as a key feature of successful retirement. New activities tend to compensate for roles that are lost as the individual ages, while leisure values tend to replace work values in maintaining activity level. This theory is relevant to this study because it shows that an individual who suffers job loss, mandatory or voluntary retirement will seek for a substitute in order to remain relevant and keep fit which is in line with what pre-retirement counselling is all about. Without activity, the human machine remains unexploited, unchallenged and deteriorates faster than it should. Hence, both Behavioural Counselling theory and the Activity theory are relevant to this study because they provide an understanding of how retirees' behaviour and the activities they engage in after active service will influence their livelihood. Secondly, the choice of the two theories in this study is:

Behavioural theory is tied to change in behaviour by adjusting from all the privileges enjoyed during active service such as full salary and allowances, housing, training, other incentives and so on. These privilege and benefits are not available after active service. The implication to this theory is that, a retiree maybe privileged to gain all the counselling idea by changing behaviour and yet not putting it to use to better his/her life. This is a major limitation.

On the other hand, the Activity theory centres on maintaining activity level. This implies that a retiree should be able to sustain what he/she is used to doing during retirement or loss of job in other to keep fit if not the retiree will waste away. Therefore, by engaging in an activity, this theory will complement the behavioural theory which is limited in activity.

Going by these theories, retirees will have the required will power to adjust from their previous life in order to reduce the risk of psychosocial problems faced by retirees after active service and engage in an activity (economic or recreational) that will earn them extra income and happiness rather than relying on their pension. Therefore, this theory is relevant to this study "Effect Retirement Counselling on Health, Economic and Sociological Adjustments of tertiary institution staff of Taraba State, Nigeria.

Health Adjustment of Retirees

Health according to the World Health Organization (WHO) (2019) is being in a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being. It is not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Thus, retirees, tend to face serious challenges in managing the health especially because of inability to do a constant exercise. Such category of retirees might experience some physiological illness such as stomach ulcers, heart disease, hypertension and a pressing tendency to commit suicide (Denga in Baba, Garba &

Zakariyah 2015). The Aegon Retirement Readiness Survey (2018), revealed that, health has emerged as the new frontier in retirement security. The miracles of modern science and improvements in nutrition in recent decades have made longer life expectancy the norm rather than the exception. Inspiring people to make the link between health, wealth and well-being as they age is critical to ensure future retirement preparedness. While most people consider themselves to be in 'good' or 'excellent' health today, that is unlikely to remain the case for the rest of their lives because many are failing to take the necessary steps to maintain good health. There is a clear correlation between workers who take steps to maintain good health and a person's sense of retirement readiness.

Economic Adjustment of Retirees

According to Olatunde & Awosusi (2011), Economic difficulty might be a principal factor for maladjustment among retirees. In the reality of Nigerian situation, inflation has eroded the value of the currency of Nigeria, that is, it could be safely stated that the amount being paid as pension is inadequate and it is not usually paid on time. Another seemingly problem that a retiree could face is the bureaucracy involved in the payment of pension and gratuity. At times, it requires that the retirees present themselves at the capital town of the places they have worked. Such process might involve a long queue, which might be demoralizing to such retirees. In a pathetic revelation by Adedeji (2010) as stated in the Nigerian Tribune, reported that some relieved staff of Union Bank took to the street and protested to the headquarters of the Bank in Marina over nonpayment of gratuity and retirement benefits. The retirees ought not to be exposed to hunger and deprivation before their entitlements are paid. In another development, Aborisade (2010) in the punch newspaper on screening exercise for pensioners, stated that pensioners complained about complex procedure of screening, poor listing as well as the high handedness of the Federal Government Officers coordinating the service. The submission of Retirement is a significant life change that affects various areas. The transition from a life of work to one of retirement has both practical and emotional implications (e.g. living with lower income, having many leisure hours, having to leave a familiar and a well-known world). Responding to retirement occurs on an individual and a unique basis. Literature mentioned diverse responses to this basic life change with differences in intensity and style of response among retirees (Doaa et al 2016). In a study carried out by Omoresemi in Baba et al (2015), among some Nigeria retirees, it was discovered that retirement affect the income, residence family structure or relationship between members of the family as well as the economic viability of retirees. For those who are compulsorily retired, their income is likely to be adversely affected while it might mean an economic boom for voluntary retirees. Due to limited financial sources, some retirees might not have the courage to associate with old friends and family.

One important set of economic decisions involves how people allocate their time among alternative uses. Decisions about work, retirement, leisure, and so forth, are all part of the general problem of deciding how to use time. For any particular person, the answer to this issue depends on many factors that include tastes and preferences for particular uses of time (for example, what activities are enjoyable?), employment opportunities, financial needs, health, and so on. In the face of many alternative uses of time, the individual chooses which activities to pursue and how much time to devote to each. The solution to this problem emphasizes the true economic cost of pursuing any specific action, not merely out-of-pocket expenses. Assessing the economic cost entails identifying what opportunities are fore-gone when a particular course of action is followed, and then assigning values to these alternatives. The economic cost of an activity is the value that can be assessed to the best alternative that must be foregone. For example, if a person chooses to play tennis for an hour rather than read a book during the same interval, the "cost" of an hour of tennis is the value that he or she places on the pleasure that would be derived from an hour of reading (retrieved from [www.ssa.gov>docs>ssb](http://www.ssa.gov/docs>ssb) 1/7/2020).

Sociological Effect of Retirement

Niels and Maarten (2014), expressed that, Social interactions play an important role in retirement decisions. First, individuals receive advice from a broad social environment, including family, friends and coworkers, and often, take the advice into account in their retirement plans. Moreover, they take the personal situation of their social environment into account, in particular of those who stand more close to

them. Second, workers are influenced by the retirement age of the social environment. An increased retirement age of the social environment of one year leads to approximately three months' later retirement of the individual. Niels and Maarten (2014) identified a special role for the age of 65 years, which has been the statutory pension age in the Netherlands for over fifty years. This may be related to the formation of social norms connected to specific retirement ages such as the statutory retirement age. As a consequence, an increase in the statutory retirement age, while raising the labor participation in the short run, may have a larger effect in the long run. Over the life-cycle individuals rely on each other to perform a large number of social activities, whether it be interactions with colleagues at the workplace, spending leisure time with friends and other acquaintances, or exchanging information, affection and help with family members. These social relationships typically evolve with the aging process in terms of size, composition and intensity of the relationship. (Comi, Cotira and Lucifora 2017). Providing help and support to family and friends is one form of social engagement. The effects of retirement on these activities have scarcely been investigated. Research has often been focused on only the number of contacts with close family members or friends. Baba, Garba & Zakariyah (2015), opined that, for many pre-retired workers, both in the public and private sector, maintaining a sense of identity and self-worth without a full-time job is in fact the single most difficult challenge that they have to face. This is as a result of the fact that there are no more junior officers to wait and run errand for retirees. The sudden realization that they have to do everything themselves, usually makes most retirees feel used and spent. This challenge may result in feeling of isolation, loneliness and anxiety for those who could not manage it.

Retirement at times could result in a reduction of social contact with friends, colleagues, co-workers and sometimes relatives. The reduction in the level of social interaction might lead to many hours of boredom, loneliness, solidarity reflection which sometimes could resulting some anti-social behaviour like drinking, smoking other. At times due to limited financial resources, some retirees might not have the courage to associate with old friends while for others retirement gives their family members and friends or to concentrate more on leisure activities, such as going to community gathering visiting, playing games and reading among others. (Undiyaundeye, 2016). Undiyaundeye in Baba (2010) stated that at retirement there is reduction in the individual's monthly income because of which some families may experience hardship especially if the wife has to cater for the entire family. Accommodation is also another problem some might have to quite official quarters while some might move in their personal houses. He also noted that the social relationship of the retirees and his family is affected obviously due to change in his usual pattern of life. Most of the retirees are either writing new application for jobs or taking trips to the pension board to ensure that their benefits are worked out and paid. However, to some this period will provide new opportunities to be close to family members.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest design. Quasi-experimental research is research that resembles experimental research but is not true experimental research. Like a true experiment, a quasi-experimental design aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and a dependent variable. In this study, quasi-experiments was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of retirement counselling on health, economic and sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria. The target population for this study is all the staff from ten (10) tertiary institutions in Taraba State.

Data was collected primarily using research instrument titled 'Retirement Counselling on Health, Economic and Sociological Adjustments Questionnaire' tagged (RCHESAQ). Descriptive Statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research question while paired samples t-test was used to test the hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

RESULTS

The study as projected, yielded data that divulged the effect of Retirement Counselling on health, economic and sociological adjustments of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Question One: *What is the effect of retirement counselling on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Pre and Post Test effect of retirement counselling on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statement	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Has retirement counselling addressed your concerns about maintaining health insurance coverage after retirement	2.18	1.14	3.50	.77
2	Has retirement counselling provided you with information about maintaining a healthy lifestyle in retirement	2.10	1.02	3.50	.62
3	Managing your health care needs post-retirement as a result of the counselling you received is worth it	2.17	.94	3.30	.72
4	Has retirement counselling provided useful resources for managing chronic health conditions in retirement	2.08	.94	3.45	.67
5	Retirement counselling has effectively helped you plan for potential health care costs in retirement	2.75	1.02	3.23	.72
6	Retirement counselling has helped you understand and prepare for the impact of aging on your health	2.23	1.06	2.78	1.04
7	Retirement counselling has addressed strategies for staying physically active after retirement	2.30	1.14	3.10	.77
8	Retirement counselling has provided adequate information on mental health resources available in retirement	2.17	.87	3.28	.64
9	Retirement counselling has prepared staff to cope with potential changes in physical health	2.22	.99	3.12	.78
10	I am satisfied with the health-related counselling and resources provided during retirement counselling	2.12	.92	3.13	.93
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation		2.23	1.00	3.24	0.77

Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation scores on health adjustment among tertiary institution staff. The mean health adjustment scores for pre-test was 2.23, and standard deviation of 1.00, while the mean health adjustment scores for post-test was 3.24 and standard deviation of 0.77. The mean difference of 1.01 implies that retirement counselling is effective on health adjustment among tertiary institution staff.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant effect of retirement counselling on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State

Table 2: Paired samples t-test on the effect of retirement counselling on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State

Pair	Posttest-Pretest	Paired Differences		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower			
		1.00833	.75156	.09703	.81418	1.20248	10.39259	.000

A paired samples t-test was conducted to examine the significant difference between pre-test mean scores and post-test mean scores on health adjustment. The result in Table 2 indicated that there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores on health adjustment; $t(59) = 10.392$, $p < .001$. The mean scores for pre-test was 2.23, while the mean scores for post-test was 3.24. The result implies that retirement counselling has significant effect on health adjustment among tertiary institution staff.

Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect of retirement counselling on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State is rejected.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of retirement counselling on economic adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Pre-test and Post-test effect of retirement counselling on economic adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statement	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Retirement counselling helped in understanding and planning for post-retirement financial needs	1.95	.93	3.28	.56
2	I am confident in managing finances after retirement as a result of the retirement counselling received	1.83	.96	3.45	.72
3	Retirement counselling prepares you for unexpected financial expenses in retirement	1.95	1.05	3.45	.70
4	Retirement counselling provided effective strategies for budgeting and saving for post-retirement	2.27	1.04	3.32	.79
5	Retirement counselling has assisted in understanding pension and social security benefits	2.42	.98	3.15	.84
6	Retirement counselling has impacted my ability to make informed investment decisions for retirement	2.57	1.39	2.97	.86
7	I feel prepared to manage my retirement savings and investments as a result of the counselling	2.53	1.16	3.05	.83
8	Retirement counselling has improved my understanding of tax implications related to my retirement income	2.33	1.08	2.98	.97
9	Retirement counselling has addressed concerns about inflation and its impact on my retirement funds	2.30	1.05	2.70	.94
10	I am satisfied with the financial planning resources provided during retirement counselling	2.37	1.15	2.95	.93
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation		2.25	1.08	3.13	0.81

Table 3 shows mean and standard deviation scores on economic adjustment among tertiary institution staff. The mean economic adjustment scores for pre-test was 2.25, and standard deviation of 1.08, while the mean economic adjustment scores for post-test was 3.13 and standard deviation of 0.81. The mean difference of 0.88 implies that retirement counselling is effective on health adjustment among tertiary institution staff.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant effect of retirement counselling on economic adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State

Table 4: Paired samples t-test on the significant effect of retirement counselling on economic adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State

Pair	Posttest-Pretest	Paired Differences						
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Sig. (2-tailed)	
					Lower	Upper		
		.87833	.74540	.09623	.68578	1.07089	9.12759	.000

A paired samples t-test was conducted to examine the significant difference between pre-test mean scores and post-test mean scores on economic adjustment. The result in Table 4 indicated that there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores on economic adjustment; $t(59) = 9.127$, $p < .001$. The mean scores for pre-test was 2.23, while the mean scores for post-test was 3.24. The result

implies that retirement counselling has significant effect on economic adjustment among tertiary institution staff. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect of retirement counselling on economic adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State is rejected.

Research Question Three: *What is the effect of retirement counselling on sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria?*

Table 5. Effect of retirement counselling on sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statement	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Retirement counselling will helped me plan for maintaining social connections after retirement	2.13	.89	3.37	.66
2	Retirement counselling has effectively addressed the potential social challenges I may face after retirement	2.33	.91	3.42	.67
3	I feel prepared to engage in community activities and social networks after retirement as a result of the counselling	2.27	.78	3.33	.71
4	Retirement counselling has provided guidance on finding new hobbies or interests to pursue in retirement	2.10	1.15	3.18	.77
5	Retirement counselling has helped to address concerns about social isolation in retirement	2.30	.94	3.12	.88
6	Retirement counselling has helped me prepare for changes in social role and identity for post-retirement	2.43	.93	3.10	.95
7	Retirement counselling has provided useful strategies for maintaining relationships with former colleagues and friends	2.63	1.12	3.20	.78
8	Retirement counselling has addressed the importance of volunteer work or community involvement after retirement	2.50	1.03	3.07	.97
9	I am satisfied with the social adjustment support provided during retirement counselling	2.50	1.07	3.23	.74
10	I am confident in my ability to build a fulfilling social life after retirement as a result of the counselling you received	2.13	.81	3.17	.85
Cluster Mean/Standard Deviation		2.23	0.96	3.22	0.80

Table 5 shows mean and standard deviation scores on sociological adjustment among tertiary institution staff. The mean sociological adjustment scores for pre-test was 2.23, and standard deviation of 0.96, while the mean economic adjustment scores for post-test was 3.22 and standard deviation of 0.80. The mean difference of 0.99 implies that retirement counselling is effective on sociological adjustment among tertiary institution staff.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant effect of retirement counselling on sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State

Table 6: Paired samples t-tset on the effect of retirement counselling on sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State

		Paired Differences						
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		Sig. (2-tailed)	
					Lower	Upper		t
Pair	Posttest-Pretest	.88500	.78844	.10179	.68132	1.08868	8.69559	.000

A paired samples t-test was conducted to examine the significant difference between pre-test mean scores and post-test mean scores on sociological adjustment. The result in Table 6 indicated that there is a significant difference between pre-test and post-test mean scores on sociological adjustment; $t(59) = 8.695$, $p < .001$. The mean scores for pre-test was 2.23, while the mean scores for post-test was 3.22. The

result implies that retirement counselling has significant effect on sociological adjustment among tertiary institution staff. Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant effect of retirement counselling on sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State is rejected.

This study investigated the Effect of Retirement Counselling on Health, Economic and Sociological Adjustments of Tertiary Institution Staff in Taraba State, Nigeria Answers to all research questions raised and hypotheses formulated have been clarified by the study. Thus, the findings of the study are discussed below.

The result of the analysis in table 1 reveals that retirement counselling has significant effect on on health adjustment of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria. The empirical literature supports the efficacy of retirement counselling approach in enhancing health adjustment of tertiary institution staff.

For instance, Denga in Baba, Garba & Zakariyah (2015) noted that, retirees, face serious challenges in managing the health especially because of inability to do a constant exercise. Such category of retirees end up experience some physiological illness such as stomach ulcers, heart disease, hypertension and a pressing tendency to commit suicide. Similarly, The Aegon Retirement Readiness Survey (2018), revealed that, health has emerged as the new frontier in retirement security. Therefore, the miracles of modern science and improvements in nutrition in recent decades have made longer life expectancy the norm rather than the exception. Inspiring people to make the link between health, wealth and well-being as they age is critical to ensure future retirement preparedness. The scholars reported significant improvements after the treatment was utilized, thus reinforcing the notion that retirement counselling approach can effectively address health issues prevalent among tertiary institution staff.

Another study by Olatunde & Awosusi (2011), revealed that Economic difficulty might be a principal factor for maladjustment among retirees. In the reality of Nigerian situation, inflation has eroded the value of the currency of Nigeria, that is, it could be safely stated that the amount being paid as pension is inadequate and it is not usually paid on time. This is in agreement with current current study.

Finally, Niels and Maarten (2014), expressed that, Social interactions play an important role in retirement decisions. First, individuals receive counsel from a broad social environment, including family, friends and coworkers, and often, take the advice into account in their retirement plans. Retirement counselling has proven to be also effective in the sociological adjustment of tertiary institution staff. This is well supported by the study conducted by Menchak, et-al (2023).

CONCLUSION

The effect of retirement counselling on health, economic and sociological adjustments of tertiary institution staff in Taraba State, Nigeria, was examined in this study. Based on the study's results, the researchers concluded that participants' health, economic and sociological adjustments were considerably enhanced by Retirement Counselling approach.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers based on the findings, recommend the following:

1. Health Counsellors/Practitioners should be trained to utilize retirement counselling practices alongside conventional methods to create a more inclusive and effective therapeutic environment on health adjustments of tertiary institution staff .
2. The Government and NGOs should utilize the use of retirement counselling techniques to provide economic support for tertiary institution staff.
3. The Government should liaise with professional counsellors to use local knowledge in addressing sociological challenges by providing help and support to family and friends as a form of social engagement.

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